

FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE PROVISION OF REMOTE BANKING SERVICES BY COMMERCIAL BANKS

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ANNOTATION

The article lists internal and external factors that affect the development of remote banking services. The article covers problems in the development of remote banking services and presents author's approaches to their elimination.

Base words: *remote banking services, internet site, risk, banking technologies, internet speed, financial services.*

Introduction. Although the provision of remote banking services in commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan is developing from year to year, it cannot be said that there are no problems in the further development of these services. It is possible to achieve an increase in the number of customers by eliminating the problems that have arisen in remote banking services and creating facilities in the program.

In addition to problems, the development of remote banking services in commercial banks is influenced by several factors. Nevertheless, a number of regulatory legal acts have been developed and intensive work is being carried out on the development of remote banking services in the banking system of our country. Today, banks are trying to increase their income as well, as a result of increasing the

number of their customers, attracting a large number of customers and increasing the quality of services provided to them. From the experience of developed countries in particular, it can be seen that the quality of remote banking services in the financial services market today determines the success of the competitive struggle in customer service.

Relevance of the topic. In the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2018 "on measures to radically improve the activities of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan" PF-5296, the creation of an effective information exchange system of commercial banks with the provision of remote banking services, which allows for the further development of the payment system, including the rapid management of This is evidenced by the relevance of the topic of research on the need to improve the quality composition of remote services provided by commercial banks and the introduction of new modern services.

The imposition of the problem. Recently, the rapid development of digital technologies around the world has been accelerating the processes of revolution in the information sector and globalization of the economy. In particular, the insufficient development of digital technologies and remote banking services in the banking system of Uzbekistan requires the study of problems in this regard.

Research objective. Scientific and practical proposals were developed by the author on the basis of decrees and decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the elimination of problems in the development of remote banking services in commercial banks, experience of developed countries and scientific research of foreign economists.

Research techniques. In the process of preparing a scientific article, methods of comparative analysis of data on the basis of tables, data grouping, analysis of influencing factors and statistical grouping based on systematic analysis, as well as expert assessment were also used most efficiently.

Key results. The provision of remote banking services to customers of banks is considered one of the most promising areas of development of the modern banking

system, and its development is influenced by a number of factors. In the development of remote banking services, it is necessary to take into account the factors affecting these services. These influencing factors can be divided into two, namely internal and external. Table 1 divides the factors affecting remote banking services into external and internal factors. It is important for the bank to study the impact of existing factors on the provision of remote banking services and maintain its correct system.

Internal factors affecting the development of remote banking services include:

First of all, we can get factors related to the organization of remote banking services to internal factors. That is, in the implementation of each remote banking service, some new technologies are implemented by introducing the capabilities of the banking system or using its capabilities in the bank. Therefore, banks in the first place should be fully equipped with banking technologies for the organization of an electronic payment system and automation of banking activities. Then the system implemented with these technologies should be simple for users, that is, it should be created to the extent that even a population with a high financial culture and less technological knowledge can use it. In addition, the security of their personal data must be fully ensured by the system creators in order for users to have confidence in this system.

Secondly, in order to popularize remote banking services, it is required to conduct the marketing policy of the bank wisely. According to him, it is important to make a positive impression on those who are interested in these services by conducting seminar trainings to lead the range of remote banking services and their capabilities to bank customers and the population. Advertising these services will also have great effect by posting videos about crowded places, internet sites, social networks, television and remote banking services in the front offices and halls of the bank that work with customers.

In addition to the factors affecting the development of the above remote banking services, it is necessary to eliminate several more problematic cases.

First, locals prefer direct communication with more bank employees when performing their operations in banks, and are used to receiving supporting documents on each of the operations performed. This situation requires the population to carry out explanatory work on the imko intentions and safety of remote banking services in order to change the mentality of the population.

Secondly, many people are hovering in the first use of new modern technology and system due to the scarcity of their understanding of new remote banking services, since each new software technology presents some difficulties in its initial use. Also, banks are constantly improving the types of services in their software systems. During the improvement, banks should also try to simplify programs a little for users, otherwise it will be a challenge for the part of customers who lack technological skills. Therefore, the creation of easy-to-use and multifunctional systems by at-Specialists of each bank will have provided their customers with effective services in a competitive environment.

Thirdly, the frequent blackout of electricity in remote districts of our Republic and, as a result, it is impossible to provide customers with timely communication service and other financial services. The fact that the speed of the internet in such places is very low causes all sorts of misunderstandings when using remote banking services. In these areas, bank customers still carry out their banking practice in full bank. Then. banks should also focus on the introduction of remote banking services in these regions.

Fourth, for the purchase and installation of modern technologies and software for commercial banks at a slightly higher cost, the fact that banks introduce their own special applications based on smartphones and computers allows you to create new opportunities in remote banking services, saving costs. It places great responsibility on the information technology professionals and programmers of banks or requires the support of other local professionals.

Fifth, while communication and the internet work 24 hours a day to bring remote banking services to the modern level, through remote banking services,

customers can use the transfer of payments until the closing of the Transaction Day. If customers are customers of different banks, payments can be made only on the current day up to 1700 hours. That is, remote banking services, like traditional services, are used by the central bank's Main Center for Informatization until the specified time.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, to create a mechanism to promote the widespread introduction of modern Information Communication Technologies in the relationship between the bank and the client, including the introduction of financial services based on electronic digital technologies with relatively low costs, the opening of 24/7-mode smartofis in all bank branches throughout the Republic, as well as bank cards and equipment serving them (payment terminal, by dramatically increasing the number of infokiosk and ATMs), the offer of convenient services for bank customers and residents of our country is considered an urgent issue today.

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